

The Soil Re-Union Science for Healthy Soils

4th International and
16th National Congress
of the Serbian Society
of Soil Science

Serbian
Society of
Soil Science

THE BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Vrdnik, Fruške Terme, Serbia,
20-23. October 2025

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Soil ReUnion: Science speaks – a call to united action

Humanity faces a triple crisis: climate change, biodiversity loss, and pollution. The international community is working intensively to address these challenges, and science confirms that the *wise use of soil* remains one of the most effective levers for protecting ecosystems and advancing climate action. Soil is, more than ever, at the center of global attention, both a joy and a responsibility for all of us who care for it.

The Soil ReUnion Congress, though not a massive world assembly, carries big ideas. Its ambition, as an initial spark, is to contribute to the global effort of responding to the triple crisis, through a triple unification, bringing together: sectors, regions, and disciplines around soil.

Agriculture, in particular, is increasingly recognized as a field that can both mitigate and adapt to climate change through regenerative practices - creating an entire *generation of regeneration*. This transition requires practical knowledge, faster research, and innovative approaches such as Living Labs, since we no longer have time for a “trial and error” approach. And let us not forget: 95% of the world’s food comes from soil, and despite technological advancements, there is no energy sustainable alternative that could ever fully replace agricultural land.

Our congress brings together scientists, decision-makers, business representatives, and global initiatives to contribute voices, ideas, and perspectives that can enrich the broader movement for soil protection. Its impact is designed to extend beyond the event itself - creating a unique community of like-minded professionals through a vibrant social program, project presentations, and our innovative π to π format: project-to-project speed blind dates.

The congress goals provide a clear framework - and we warmly invite you to find your place within it, connect with others, and make the most of every opportunity it offers, including:

- transferring scientific knowledge to bridge science, industry, and policy;
- creating a platform for dialogue to enable cooperation and co-creation of future strategies; and
- establishing thematic networks to ensure ongoing knowledge exchange and advance soil protection beyond the event.

Welcome - and thank you for being part of this shared contribution!

Dr Jordana Ninkov, president of Organization committee

Dr Snežana Jakšić, president of Program committee

Dr Jovica Vasin, president of Scientific committee and president of Serbian Society of Soil Science

EXCERPT FROM THE CONGRESS PROGRAMME

This extract from the official Congress Programme captures the spirit and concept of the Congress. The complete and detailed programme has been published separately.

Duration: 20–23 October 2025

Venue: Fruške Terme Hotel, Vrdnik, Serbia

Congress Centre: IV Floor, Wing B

Monday, 20 October 2025

Late afternoon

Registration

Fireside chat and interactive discussion

Dinner

Welcome party

Tuesday, 21 October 2025

Morning session

Registration

Official ceremonial opening of the Congress

Pause, Project exhibitions tour

Pause, Poster viewing session

Plenary lectures – Keynote speakers

Parallel oral presentations

Lunch

Pause for forest walk or relaxation

Afternoon session

Interactive workshop on innovative techniques in soil analysis and nutrient management (Sponsors' exhibition)

π to π (Project-to-Project) speed blind date

Dinner

Social gathering

Wednesday, 22 October 2025

Registration

Parallel oral presentations

Pause, Poster viewing session

Poster section with three-minute talks

Lunch

Assembly of the Serbian Society of Soil Science

Pause for forest walk or relaxation

Gala dinner

Thursday, 23 October 2025

Expert and tourist excursion – one-day

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(in alphabetical order)

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ORGANIC AMENDMENTS AND PESTICIDE RETENTION IN SOILS

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ABSTRACT

To evaluate how organic soil amendments (OSAs) influence pesticide retention, batch adsorption experiments were carried out with sandy amended alluvial soil from the Danube River. Three organic materials were tested as amendments: biochar, obtained from *Miscanthus giganteus* pyrolyzed at 550°C; sediment, collected from the polluted Begej Canal (containing heavy metals and organic contaminants); and compost, derived from green waste in Novi Sad. Two pesticides with contrasting properties were selected: cypermethrin, a pyrethroid insecticide, and cyprodinil, a fungicide. The sorption tests were performed under controlled laboratory conditions (20±2°C), with equilibrium established after 72h. Sorption data were fitted with the Freundlich isotherm model, which showed well correlation ($R^2 = 0.989\text{--}0.999$). The Freundlich exponent (n) varied between 0.56 and 1.28, reflecting differences in sorption favorability depending on the applied amendment. Partition coefficients (K_d), determined at three relative equilibrium concentrations ($C_e = 0.01S_w$, $0.1S_w$, $0.5S_w$), ranged from 2.2 to 5.3, confirming the role of amendment type in regulating pesticide retention.

The results emphasize that pesticide retention is not governed by a single mechanism but rather by the chemical nature of both the pesticide and the amendment. While cyprodinil sorption was promoted through specific interactions, cypermethrin retention was driven mainly by hydrophobic forces. These variations underline the complexity of pesticide–soil amendment interactions and the importance of selecting amendment strategies tailored to the properties of individual pesticides.

Overall, the study demonstrates that biochar, sediment, and compost can substantially enhance pesticide sorption in soils, thereby reducing their potential mobility and leaching to groundwater. Such insights are essential for the design of sustainable soil management practices that both mitigate environmental contamination and preserve soil health.

Keywords: organic soil amendments, pesticide sorption, groundwater protection

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